

Greener Journal of Internet, Information and Communication Systems

ISSN: 2354-2373

Submitted: 19/01/2017

Accepted: 26/01/2017

Published: 06/04/2017

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJIICS.2017.1.011917007>

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By

**Olaifa, Taye Paul
Uzokwe, Chuka Christian
Oyeniya, Janet O
Edache, Rose**

Research Article (DOI: <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJIICS.2017.1.011917007>)

Peculiarities in Agricultural Book Publishing: Case Study of National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) Library Collections

Olaifa, Taye Paul*; Uzokwe, Chuka Christian; Oyeniyi, Janet O; and Edache Rose

National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) Library, P.M.B. 1525, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: ejipaul1@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The paper seeks to investigate the nature and features of agricultural book publishing in Nigeria, using National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) Library-Collections as a case study. The research examines a book publishing features such as collaborations, positions of authors, gender, etc. More importantly, this research tends to study the history of book publishing in Nigeria as it translates to Nigerian library's collection. The research specifically considered what percentage of research library collections are published in the country, and also authored by Nigerians.

Keywords: Agriculture, Book Publishing, Library, NCAM.

INTRODUCTION

The word 'book' or 'textbook' plays a key role in research. Books form the foundation of any research. Book is defined by the Merriam-Webster dictionary (2016) as a set of printed sheets of paper that are held together inside a cover: a long written work. Oyeniyi et al (2014) stated that books are critical to the success of educational process and research development. Books are instruments of culture and indispensable aids to personal cultivation. While reiterating the importance of books, Dr Alex Ekweme, a former vice president of the federal republic of Nigeria in his opening speech at the first Nigerian National Congress on Book held in Lagos, in 1983 reiterated that:

"Education is the backbone of national development, and the book is the principal element in the educational process, books are vital for both teaching and learning at every level of education" Books serve as instruments of communicating information and ideas."

Book publishing is thus an important process of production and dissemination of information and idea. Books are published in every area of human knowledge. Books however form a non - negligible aspect of the study of the library. Many traditionalists have defined libraries as a place where books are kept for reading and consultation. Whether this definition is complete or not, it certainly focused on a singular fact that the book is synonymous to the library. Every library must have collections, which must include books.

Agricultural book publishing simply focuses on books that are produced in favour of the subject - agriculture.

Agricultural books / textbooks form the major and dominating part of the collections of a type of library called "Agricultural libraries" which are domiciled in agricultural based institutes or colleges.

A BRIEF ON NCAM LIBRARY

The National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) is an agricultural based research institute in Nigeria, which was established in 1990. NCAM library is therefore a research library, stocked with agricultural and engineering related research materials in-line with the mandate of the institution, for the purpose of promoting agricultural mechanization, research and development in Nigeria, and Africa at large.

The library acquires both print and non-print research materials in Agriculture, Mechanization, Sciences, Engineering, Management and Social Sciences. The library which has both virtual and e-library sections has various collections covering textbooks, journals, research reports, publications and many other print and non-print materials.

NCAM library uses an 'In-House' classification scheme, which covers areas like, Land and Water Engineering, Farm Power and Machinery, Processing and Storage, Mechanics, General agriculture, Sciences, Workshop Technology, Chemical Engineering, Electrical Engineering etc.

BOOK PUBLISHING IN NIGERIA

The History of book publishing in Nigeria can be traced to the establishment of university college, Ibadan (UCI) in 1946. According to Ajeluorou (2014), the university was bound to compete with some of the leading publishers from the United Kingdom such as Longman, Heinemann, Oxford University Press, and Cambridge University Press.

Chukwuemeka (2004) also noted that Nigeria had the longest number of publishing houses in any African Country at that time. This position was initiated through the government establishment of paper and pulp making industries, which has over time led to the production of books in various subjects covering the primary, secondary and tertiary section of the educational system.

Chukwuemeka [2004] however observed that the established paper and pulp making industries by the federal government collapsed as a result of the economic downturn in the 1980s which has since resulted in book famine in the country. In a similar opinion, Ajeluorou (2014) added that the economic downturn in the 1980s was as a result of the introduction of Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) by the government in 1986.

As a result of the economic downturn, the foreign publisher pulled out of the publishing business, making it difficult for the local publishers to sustain the business. The economic downturn also led to low purchasing power which radically dropped purchase of books.

Since the downturn of the economy in 1980s and its negative effect on the publishing business, the government has organized several conferences, workshops, committees and task forces for the purpose of reviving the publishing sector. Some of the task forces, as noted by Chukwuemeka (2004) are: Task force on the scarcity of books and stationary in 1984, 1987 panel on a book policy in Nigeria, 1990 National council on education committee report on Rationalization of textbooks in primary and secondary schools, 1990 Ministerial Committee on Provision of books to schools and colleges, 1993 Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council Review Workshop on preferred recommendation for solving the problems of the Nigerian Book industry and formation of implementation strategies, 1994 National Conference on Book Development etc.

Despite these several efforts by the government to resuscitate the book industry in the country, Nigeria today, is still faced with major setbacks and challenges in the industry. This has prompted some Linguist and African language experts like Prof. Emmanuel Nnolue Emenanjo quoted in Ajeluorou (2014) to proclaim in a recent lecture:

"Nigeria is a chronically bookless country and most Nigerians are neither great lovers; great buyers, avid readers, nor fanatical users of books"

"Nigeria produces less than one percent of her actual book needs, which should now stand at some 199.76 million books per year."

"Nigerians have the lowest rate of paper consumption in the world with only 3kdos of printed materials per person, per year as against South Africa, with 100 kilos, Europeans with 250 kilos, Americans with 270 kilos and Japanese with 300 kilos.

The country is now filled with several small publishing industries that cannot compete with the firms found in advanced countries in Europe, America, Asia, etc.

The effect of these on our libraries' collections has been the fact that a large percentage of our research library collections are published by foreign publishers in foreign countries and mostly by foreign authors. These textbooks are often acquired in our library through agents or online transactions in exorbitant prices. These developments have posed a negative impact on our economy.

RESEARCH QUESTION

What percentage of textbooks in Nigerian research libraries are published in Nigeria?

What percentage of textbooks in Nigerian research library is authored by Nigerians?

METHODOLOGY

NCAM library collection serves as a data for this research study. Though the library has a reasonably large collection of both print and non-print materials, the writer however selected 464 textbooks randomly from the library's collection. Being a research library, the largest percentage of her collections are Journals and research reports. However, only the textbooks in the library collections are used for this research. The textbooks cover areas such as Science & Technology, Engineering, Mechanization and General Agriculture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Year-wise distribution of textbook publications

S/No	Publication Year	Total Textbooks Published	Percentage (%) of 464
1	1951-1960	4	0.9
2	1961-1970	9	1.9
3	1971-1980	36	7.8
4	1981-1990	78	16.8
5	1991-2000	49	10.6
6	2001-2010	213	45.9
7	2011-2014	75	16.2
Total		464	100.0

Table 1 above shows the year-wise distribution of textbook publications used for this research. The table shows the breakdown of a table of 464 text books covering 63years (1951-2014). 2001-2010 has the highest textbooks (213) 45.9% while 1951- 1960 has the lowest with just 4 textbooks out of the entire collections. The data covers both old and recently published textbooks so as to ascertain if there is any significant difference in book publishing for the periods.

Table 2: ANALYSIS OF THE PLACE OF PUBLICATION

S/No	Area	INDIA	Malaysia	RUSSIA	USA	NIGERIA	UK	NA	OTHERS	TOTAL
1	FARM POWER AND MACHINERY	14	0	2	6	2	2	1	3	30
2	LAND AND WATER ENGINEERING	40	0	1	30	2	10	1	3	87
3	ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING	4	0	0	19	1	8	1	0	33
4	CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	5
5	PROCESSING AND STORAGE	32	0	0	5	3	2	0	3	45
6	SCIENCES	0	0	0	11	0	4	0	0	15
7	MECHANICS	10	0	1	20	2	3	0	6	42
8	ACHITECTURE & CIVIL ENGINEERING	5	0	0	22	0	14	1	2	44
9	GENERAL AGICULTURE	83	7	0	6	3	8	4	8	119
10	WORKSHOP TECHNOLOGY	5	3	6	7	1	18	0	4	44
Total		194	10	10	130	14	69	8	29	464

Table 2 above shows the analysis of the place of publication of the textbooks. It is clear from the table that almost all the textbooks are published outside Nigeria and even the African continent. Out of the total of 464 textbooks, 194 were published in India, 130 in USA, 69 were published in UK, and 14 out of the textbooks were published in Nigeria. Only about 3% of the entire textbooks used for this research are published in Nigeria. This points a big set-back in Nigeria's publishing industry. This result agrees with the findings of Oyeniyi & Opaleke (2012) who also affirmed that most of Nigerian authors prefer to publish their works abroad; only very few Nigerians would not mind to publish their work locally. They further noted that most of the Nigerian authors prefer publishing abroad because they believe publishing abroad earn more prestige and profit (foreign exchange in dollar for royalty)

Table 3: High Contributing Publishers with more than 9 Textbooks

S/NO	Name of Publisher	No of Books
1	Mc Graw Hill	42
2	Pearson	32
3	CBS publishers and distributors	20
4	Daya Publishers	19
5	Elsevier	19
6	Gene tech Book.	19
7	Macmillan	19
8	Biotech books	17
9	PHI Learn up private limited	16
10	APH publishing co-operation	11
11	John Wiley & Sons. Inc	11
12	Newnes	11
13	Mir publisher Moscow	10

Table 3 above shows the list of publishers that have more than nine (9) textbooks in the 464 textbooks used for this research. McGraw Hill publisher has the highest textbooks (42), followed by Pearson Publishers, and CBS Publishers. In total, 13 publishers made the list out of which there is no single Nigerian publisher. This agrees with the result shown in table 2, where only about 3% of the entire textbooks used for this research are published in Nigeria. This result reiterates a set-back in Nigerian and African research development.

Table 4: Nigerian Authors vs. Foreign Authors

S/NO	AREAS	NO OF NIGERIAN AUTHORS	NO OF FOREIGN AUTHORS	TOTAL NO OF AUTHORS	% OF NIGERIAN AUTHORS	% OF FOREIGN AUTHORS
1	FARM POWER AND MACHINERY	1	59	60	0.12	7.4
2	LAND AND WATER ENGINEERING	3	160	163	0.37	20.0
3	ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING	5	45	50	0.62	5.6
4	CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	0	13	13	0.00	1.6
5	PROCESSING AND STORAGE	5	64	69	0.62	8.0
6	SCIENCES	0	37	37	0.00	4.6
7	MECHANICS	3	59	62	0.37	7.4
8	ACHITECTURE & CIVIL ENGINEERING	0	69	69	0.00	8.6
9	GENERAL AGICULTURE	8	203	211	1.00	25.3
10	WORKSHOP TECHNOLOGY	4	64	68	0.50	8.0
TOTAL		29	773	802	3.62%	96.4%

Table 4 shows a comparison analysis of Nigerian authors and the foreign authors. A total of 802 authors were recorded for the 454 textbooks. This implies a good level of collaboration in textbook publishing. This is in agreement with Oyeniyi & Olaifa (2012) that collaboration is a common phenomenon in research. The table confirms that research and development, which translate to book publishing, are dominated by foreign authors and publishers. As recorded in the table, only 29(3.62%) out of the total 802 authors are Nigerians, while 773 (96.4%) out of the 802 authors are foreign authors.

CONCLUSION

Research and publication does not only contribute to the economic, social and political emancipation of an individual, but also and more importantly to the nation as a whole. The dominance of foreign research on research and development in Nigeria is becoming alarming. This has become evident in the type of textbooks available in most Nigerian libraries today as shown in the result and findings of this paper.

The bottom line is: There are more foreign textbooks and foreign authors on our library shelves than the Nigerian authors or textbooks. However, various factors have accounted for this disparity, and thus a need for immediate action.

Firstly, there is need to have a working policy on research and publication that will encourage both the researcher and the publishing firm.

There should be a symbiotic relationship between the Nigerian researcher and the publishing firms, which must be sponsored by the government. In other words, government must be willing to fund research up to the level of textbook / book publication for all categories of researchers, especially in research institutes and other academic institutions. Government should also encourage the Nigerian publishing industry through policies that will reduce their cost of production, tax, and creates a more enabling environment for the business.

The future of any Nation is largely dependent on research, the final stages of research documentation in form of textbooks, journals, etc. It is however, important for the Government to encourage research by encouraging researchers so as to ensure a secured future for the Nation.

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Cite this Article: Olaifa TP; Uzokwe CC, Oyeniya JO and Edache R (2017). Peculiarities in Agricultural Book Publishing: Case Study of National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) Library Collections. *Greener Journal of Internet, Information and Communication Systems*, 3(1): 009-013, <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJIICS.2017.1.011917007>